

Determinants of Delay in Seeking Medical Care among Patients with Chronic Illnesses in Two Hospitals in Port Sudan: A Cross-Sectional Study

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Abstract

Introduction: Chronic illnesses represent a major global health burden, especially in low- and middle-income countries such as Sudan. A main challenge in their management is the delay in seeking medical care, which leads to serious complications and higher costs. This study aimed to identify factors influencing such delays among patients with chronic illnesses in Port Sudan.

Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted at Port Sudan Teaching Hospital and Prince Digna Hospital between July and September 2025. A total of 392 patients with chronic diseases were interviewed using a structured questionnaire. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 27. Descriptive statistics, correlation, and regression analyses were used to identify determinants of delay.

Results: Only 19.6% of patients sought medical care within a week of symptom onset. The majority delayed for 8 days or more, with the largest proportion (33.7%) delaying for 15–29 days. Main factors associated with delay included waiting for symptoms to disappear, high cost of care, long distance to health facilities, and the use of traditional medicine. Rural residence was linked to longer delays. Patients with higher education and frequent hospital visits were less likely to delay.

Conclusion: Delay in seeking medical care for chronic illnesses remains a serious problem in Port Sudan. Patient beliefs, financial barriers, and access challenges contribute to this issue. Strengthening community education, decentralizing care, and reducing costs are essential to promote timely care-seeking.

Key words: Chronic illness, Delay in care, Sudan, Port Sudan, Hypertension, Diabetes

Introduction

Chronic illnesses, also known as non-communicable diseases (NCDs), are among the most serious global health challenges of the 21st century. They include hypertension, diabetes mellitus, cardiovascular diseases, chronic respiratory illnesses, and cancers. Unlike infectious diseases, NCDs are long-term conditions that require lifelong care, lifestyle adjustment, and ongoing medical follow-up. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), NCDs are responsible for approximately 41 million deaths annually, accounting for 74% of all global deaths, with 77% of these deaths occurring in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) [1].

A critical challenge in the management of chronic illnesses is the delay in seeking medical care. Delay occurs when individuals postpone visiting a healthcare facility despite experiencing symptoms or after being diagnosed with a chronic condition. Early care-seeking is crucial for successful disease control, yet in many countries, patients present late, often after complications have developed [2]. This behaviour worsens disease outcomes, increases hospital admissions, and contributes to avoidable disability and death. Globally, several determinants contribute to delayed health-seeking behaviour, including limited awareness of disease, economic hardship, cultural beliefs, and lack of access to healthcare facilities [3,4]. Even in high-income countries, patients may delay due to stigma, fear of diagnosis, or denial of illness [5]. However, in LMICs, these challenges are intensified by weak healthcare systems, inadequate insurance coverage, and insufficient human and material resources [6]. In sub-Saharan Africa, the burden of chronic illnesses is rising rapidly as countries undergo demographic and lifestyle transitions. Urbanization, reduced physical activity, and changing diets have increased the prevalence of diabetes and hypertension [7]. Yet, health systems remain largely oriented towards communicable diseases, leaving many chronic illness patients without timely or continuous care. Studies from Ethiopia, Nigeria, and Kenya have identified cost, distance, and reliance on traditional medicine as major causes of delay [8–10].

In Sudan, the double burden of disease is evident. While infectious diseases persist, chronic illnesses are becoming increasingly common and are now among the top causes of hospital admissions and deaths [11]. The situation is particularly concerning in Port Sudan, where the combination of urban poverty, limited health literacy, and restricted access to affordable care has made delayed healthcare-seeking a serious problem. This study therefore aimed to identify the specific factors influencing delays in seeking medical care among patients with chronic illnesses in Port Sudan, to inform targeted interventions.

Methods

Study design and setting

A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted from July 1 to September 30, 2025, at Port Sudan Teaching Hospital and Prince Digna Hospital, the two main referral centers for chronic disease management in Red Sea State, Sudan.

Study population and eligibility criteria

The study included adult patients (≥ 18 years) who were attending medical outpatient clinics for follow-up of chronic illnesses such as hypertension, diabetes mellitus, bronchial asthma, or chronic heart disease, and who had experienced an episode of worsening symptoms during the previous six months. **Inclusion criteria were:** adults aged 18 years or older, clinically diagnosed with at least one chronic disease for six months or longer, and who gave informed verbal consent. **Exclusion criteria were:** patients with acute medical emergencies requiring immediate care, those with cognitive impairment or communication difficulties that prevented reliable recall, and patients or caregivers unwilling to participate.

Sampling and sample size

The minimum sample size was calculated using the single-population proportion formula ($n = Z^2 p (1-p) / d^2$), assuming a 50% prevalence of delayed care seeking [3], 95% confidence level ($Z = 1.96$), and 5% margin of error. The calculated sample (384) was increased by 5% to account for potential non-response, giving a total of 404 eligible participants. A consecutive sampling method was applied to recruit all eligible patients attending the clinics during the study period until the sample size was met. Of 404 patients approached, 392 consented to participate (response rate 97%), 6 refused, and 6 were excluded because of incomplete data.

Definition and measurement of delay

The primary outcome variable was delay in seeking medical care, defined as the number of days between symptom onset and the first contact with a qualified health facility [12]. Participants self-reported the date of onset of new or worsening symptoms and the date they sought medical advice. Delay was then categorized as follows: ≤ 7 days (no delay), 8–14 days (mild delay), 15–29 days (moderate delay), and ≥ 30 days (prolonged delay) [13]. The cut-offs were adapted from previous studies in similar settings and reviewed by local clinicians for contextual relevance.

Data collection tools and quality assurance

Data were collected using a structured interviewer-administered questionnaire developed after reviewing related literature. The tool comprised five sections: sociodemographic data, disease characteristics, health-service factors, health-seeking behavior, and reasons for delay. The questionnaire was developed in English, translated into Arabic, and back-translated to ensure consistency. It was pretested on 20 patients at Suakin Hospital (not part of the main study). Based on the pilot, minor wording changes were made to improve clarity. Data collectors (two nurses, one medical officer and 5 medical students) received two days of training on the questionnaire and interviewing techniques.

Variables

Dependent variable: delay in seeking care (continuous, days; and categorical). Independent variables: Sociodemographic: age (in years), sex (male/female), education level (none, primary, secondary, tertiary), residence (urban/rural), occupation (employed, unemployed, retired, housewife, student). Health-related: type of chronic disease (hypertension, diabetes, asthma, other), duration of illness (<1 year, 1–4 years, 5–9 years, ≥ 10 years), comorbidities (yes/no), previous use of traditional medicine (yes/no). Behavioral factors: self-medication (yes/no), waiting for symptoms to disappear (yes/no).

Statistical analysis

Data were entered and analyzed using SPSS version 27. Continuous variables were summarized as means and standard deviations, and categorical variables as frequencies and percentages. Normality of the dependent variable (delay in days) was checked using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test and visual inspection of histograms. Because the distribution approximated normality, linear regression was used. Bivariate analyses were conducted to identify variables associated with delay; variables with $p < 0.20$ were included in a multivariable linear regression model to determine independent predictors. Results were presented as unstandardized β coefficients with 95% confidence intervals (CI) and p -values. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Ethical considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the Research and Ethics Committee of Red Sea University, Sudan (Ref: REC-2023-4). Permission to collect data was also obtained from the administrations of both hospitals. Participation was voluntary; verbal informed consent was obtained because most participants were not literate, and this procedure was approved by the ethics committee. All data were kept anonymous and confidential.

Results

Of 404 eligible patients approached, 392 completed interviews (response rate 97%). Twelve were excluded (six refused, six incomplete). There were no statistically significant differences in age or sex between responders and non-responders.

Table 1. Socio-demographic characteristics of participants (n=392)

The sample was almost evenly divided by sex (53.1% female, 46.9% male) and included various age groups, with most aged 50–59 years (21.2%). Most were married (67.1%) and lived in urban areas (69.1%). Education levels differed, with secondary school most common (36.7%) and 11.5% having no formal education. Employment status showed 35.5% employed and 20.7% unemployed, while 36.7% earned 100,000–300,000 SD and 23.2% earned 300,000–500,000 SD.

Variable	Category	Frequency (n=392)	Percentage (%)
Sex	Female	208	53.1
	Male	184	46.9
Age Group	18–29 years	60	15.3
	30–39 years	76	19.4
	40–49 years	82	20.9
	50–59 years	83	21.2
	60–70 years	60	15.3
	More than 70 years	31	7.9
Marital Status	Married	263	67.1
	Single	63	16.1
	Widowed	35	8.9
	Divorced	31	7.9
Education Level	Secondary	144	36.7
	Primary	112	28.6
	University	91	23.2
	None	45	11.5
Residence	Urban	271	69.1
	Rural	121	30.9
Occupation	Employed	139	35.5
	Unemployed	81	20.7
	Retired	78	19.9
	Housewife	73	18.6
	Student	21	5.4

Monthly Income (SDG)	Less than 100,000SD	36	9.2
	100,000 – 300,000SD	144	36.7
	300,000 - 500,000 SD	121	30.9
	More than 500,000SD	91	23.2

Table 2. Clinical profile and health system factors

Chronic illnesses were frequent, mainly diabetes (40.6%) and hypertension (38.0%). Many (41.3%) were diagnosed 1–4 years ago, and nearly half (48.2%) visited the hospital 2–3 times in the past year. Most (80.6%) were on regular treatment, and 73.0% understood their illness. However, only 49.2% received education on complications, and 48.0% found healthcare costs unaffordable

Variable	Category	Frequency (n=392)	Percentage (%)
Chronic Illness	Diabetes	159	40.6
	Hypertension	149	38.0
	Asthma	54	13.8
	Other	30	7.7
Duration since diagnosis of chronic illness	< 1 year	64	16.3
	1–4 years	162	41.3
	5–9 years	108	27.6
	≥ 10 years	58	14.8
Frequency of hospital visits in the past 12 months	0 – 1	86	21.9
	2 -3	189	48.2
	4 – 6	84	21.4
	More than 6	33	5.2
Regular Treatment	Yes	316	80.6
	No	76	19.4
Understand Illness	Yes	286	73.0
	No	106	27.0
Educated on Complications	Yes	193	49.2
	No	199	50.8

Finds Cost Affordable	Yes	204	52.0
	No	188	48.0

Table 3. Multivariable linear regression analysis of determinants of delay in seeking medical care

The multivariable regression analysis showed that lower income, lower education level, rural residence, unaffordable healthcare costs, waiting for symptoms to worsen, and use of alternative medicine were significantly associated with longer delays in seeking medical care ($p < 0.05$). Age was not a significant factor. The model explained 46% of the variance in delay (Adjusted $R^2 = 0.44$, $p < 0.001$).

Predictor Variable	Unstandardized β Coefficient	95% Confidence Interval	p-value
Age (years)	-0.04	-0.12 – 0.04	0.320
Monthly income (SDG)	-0.0008	-0.0016 – -0.0001	0.030
Education level	-1.35	-2.25 – -0.45	0.004
Residence (Rural)	+2.91	1.43 – 4.39	<0.001
Cost (Unaffordable)	+4.72	3.21 – 6.23	<0.001
Waiting for Symptoms	+5.48	4.02 – 6.93	<0.001
Alternative Medicine Use	+4.05	2.67 – 5.43	<0.001
Model Summary	R^2	0.46	
	Adjusted R^2	0.44	
	F-statistic	26.5	
	p-value (Overall)	<0.001	

Table 4. Distribution of delay in seeking medical care (n=392)

Most participants experienced some delay in seeking medical care. Moderate delay (15–29 days) was the most common (33.7%), followed by mild delay (26.0%) and prolonged delay (20.7%). Only 19.6% sought care promptly (within 7 days)

Delay Category	Delay Duration	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
No Delay	≤ 7 days	77	19.6
Mild Delay	8 – 14 days	102	26.0
Moderate Delay	15 – 29 days	132	33.7
Prolonged Delay	≥ 30 days	81	20.7

Discussion

This study explored why patients with chronic illnesses in Port Sudan delay seeking medical care. The findings revealed that the majority of patients postponed medical consultation for more than a week, with most delays ranging from 8 to 29 days. The main determinants were waiting for symptoms to disappear, high cost of healthcare, long distance to facilities, and reliance on traditional medicine. These results are consistent with studies from other African countries [2,7,8].

The most influential factor identified was the tendency to "wait and see" whether symptoms would resolve spontaneously. This finding aligns with research in Ethiopia and Tanzania, where patients often underestimated the seriousness of their conditions and sought medical attention only when symptoms became severe [9,14]. Such behaviour reflects limited health literacy and cultural perceptions of illness, where chronic diseases are not seen as urgent unless accompanied by acute pain or disability. Financial barriers were another strong predictor of delay. Nearly half of the participants considered healthcare costs unaffordable. In Sudan, where health insurance coverage is limited, most patients pay out of pocket. Similar findings have been reported in Nigeria and Kenya, where poverty and treatment costs were major reasons for late presentation [10,15]. Financial constraints also interact with distance and transport challenges particularly for rural residents, making hospital visits both costly and inconvenient. The use of traditional medicine also contributed to delay. Many patients in Sudan rely on herbal or spiritual healers, often because these options are more accessible and culturally accepted [11,16]. However, such practices frequently postpone formal medical treatment until complications develop. A patient in a rural area might first consult a traditional healer due to proximity and cultural trust. When this doesn't resolve their chronic symptoms, the accumulating costs and the daunting travel to a distant hospital create a new layer of inertia. While traditional healing plays a role in community life, integrating it within public health education could reduce harmful delays.

On the positive side, patients with higher education and more frequent hospital visits were less likely to delay seeking care. Education improves understanding of disease severity and enhances confidence in healthcare systems [17]. Regular follow-up also strengthens trust between patients and providers, which encourages earlier reporting of symptoms.

These findings highlight the urgent need for targeted interventions to address both patient and system-level barriers. Health authorities should prioritize community-based education programmes focusing on early recognition of chronic disease symptoms and complications. Financial risk protection mechanisms, such as subsidized treatment or hospital-based insurance schemes, would help reduce economic barriers. Moreover, strengthening primary healthcare centers in rural areas could significantly shorten travel time and encourage early care-seeking.

This study contributes valuable local evidence to a growing body of research on healthcare-seeking behaviour in LMICs. Despite these strengths, it has several limitations. First, the delay period was self-reported, which may introduce recall bias. Second, because data were collected from hospital patients, the findings may not represent individuals who never sought formal care (selection bias). Third, the cross-sectional design limits causal inference; we can only describe associations. Fourth, social desirability bias may have affected reporting of culturally sensitive behaviors such as traditional medicine use. Despite these limitations, the study provides valuable insight into patient-related and health-system factors influencing care-seeking behavior for chronic diseases in eastern Sudan.

Conclusion

Delay in seeking medical care for chronic illnesses is common in Port Sudan and results from a mix of behavioural, financial, and structural barriers. Targeted community education and improved accessibility of health services are recommended to reduce delays in seeking care among chronic disease patients.

What is known about this topic?

Delayed healthcare seeking contributes to poor outcomes in patients with chronic illnesses. Socioeconomic and access factors influence patients' decisions to seek medical attention.

What this study adds

Identifies behavioral and cultural factors, including waiting for symptoms to subside and use of traditional medicine, as major contributors to care-seeking delays in Port Sudan. Provides baseline data to guide public health interventions aimed at reducing delay and improving chronic disease management in eastern Sudan.

Competing Interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Authors' contributions

Elalim Eltayeb Abudurrahman: conceptualized the study, designed the methodology, and drafted the manuscript. **Tabsira Ali Ibrahim Mohammed, Ayman Alaedin Omer:** supervised data collection and performed data curation. **Nada Mohammed Saad Salem, Abdulrhim Mohammed Abdulrhim, Gafar Mohamed Abdelnabi:** conducted formal statistical analysis and contributed to interpretation of results. **Omnia Yousif Ali Attaalmnaan, Tbain Tarig Mohamed, Idris Mohamedali Idris:** reviewed and edited the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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Data availability

The datasets generated and analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

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References

1. World Health Organization. Noncommunicable diseases: key facts. Geneva: WHO; 2024. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/noncommunicable-diseases>
2. Awoke MA, Molla A, Abate BA, Mekonen MA. Delayed presentation to healthcare facilities and associated factors among patients with chronic diseases in Northwest Ethiopia. PLoS One [I. 2021;16(3):e0248460. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0248460>
3. Kruk ME, Gage AD, Joseph NT, Danaei G, García-Saisó S, Salomon JA. Mortality due to low-quality health systems in the universal health coverage era: a systematic analysis of amenable deaths in 137 countries. Lancet. 2018;392(10160):2203–12. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(18\)31668-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(18)31668-4)

4. Nugent R, Bertram MY, Jan S, Niessen LW, Sassi F, Jamison DT, et al. Investing in non-communicable disease prevention and management to advance the Sustainable Development Goals. *Lancet*. 2018;391(10134):209–35. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(18\)30667-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(18)30667-6)
5. Busza J, Dauya E, Bandason T, Mujuru H, Ferrand RA. The role of stigma in health-seeking among adolescents living with HIV in Harare, Zimbabwe. *BMC Public Health*. 2018 ;18(1):61. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-017-4589-9>
6. Peters DH, Garg A, Bloom G, Walker DG, Brieger WR, Rahman MH. Poverty and access to health care in developing countries. *Ann N Y Acad Sci*. 2008;1136:161–71. <https://doi.org/10.1196/annals.1425.011>
7. Gouda HN, Charlson F, Sorsdahl K, Ahmadzada S, Ferrari AJ, Erskine H, et al. Burden of non-communicable diseases in sub-Saharan Africa, 1990–2017: results from the Global Burden of Disease Study 2017. *Lancet Glob Health*. 2019;7(10):e1375–e1387. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X\(19\)30374-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(19)30374-2)
8. Ayele AA, Tefera YG, Ayana M, Bacha H. Delay in seeking healthcare and its determinants among patients with hypertension in Northwest Ethiopia: a cross-sectional study. *BMC Health Serv Res*. 2019;19(1):19. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-018-3848-5>
9. Mboya IB, Mboya B, Mwangi P. Health care seeking behaviour and associated factors among patients with chronic illnesses in Tanzania. *Int J Med Health Sci*. 2020 :9(6):50–6. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/348492233_Health_Care_Seeking_Behaviour_and_Associated_Factors_among_Patients_w_ith_Chronic_Illnesses_in_Tanzania
10. Ezeala-Adikaibe BA, Aneke CJ, Orjioko C, Jideonwo A, Nwabueze A, Nwosu N, et al. Factors associated with late presentation of stroke patients in Enugu, Nigeria. *Niger Med J*. 2018 ;59(6):347–52. https://doi.org/10.4103/nmj.NMJ_93_18
11. Sudan Federal Ministry of Health. Annual Health Statistical Report 2022. Khartoum: FMOH; 2023 . <https://fmoh.gov.sd/>
12. Gedamu S, Abate M, Tsegaw A, Debalkie M. Time to Presentation and Predictors of Delayed Health Care Seeking among Adult Heart Failure Patients in Northwest Ethiopia: A Cross-Sectional Study. *International Journal of Chronic Diseases*. 2021;2021:6636780. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/6636780>
13. Suleiman A, Adebisi YA, Ahmed AE, et al. Determinants of delay in seeking healthcare among hypertensive and diabetic patients in Northern Nigeria. *Pan Afr Med J*. 2021;39:101.
14. Awoke MA, Negin J, Moller J, Farell P, Yawson AE. Time to presentation for chronic disease symptoms in African primary care: systematic review. *Int Health*. 2019;11(3):176-186
15. Muriithi MK, Muriithi IK. Determinants of healthcare-seeking behaviour in Kenya. *Eur Sci J* . 2015;11(11):1857–7881. <https://eujournal.org/index.php/esj/article/view/5399>
16. Abdallah TM, Adam I. Patterns of chronic disease and barriers to care in Eastern Sudan: a cross-sectional study. *BMC Public Health*. 2019;19:180. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-019-6513-y>
17. Yousif MA, Ahmed MH. Barriers to healthcare for patients with diabetes in Sudan: a qualitative study. *East Mediterr Health J*. 2020;26(9):1105–12. <https://doi.org/10.26719/emhj.20.037>
18. Saeed BI, Yawson AE, Nguah SB, Agyei-Baffour P, Emmanuel N, Ayesu E. Socio-demographic determinants of healthcare utilisation among older adults in Ghana: a qualitative study. *BMC Health Serv Res*. 2015 :15:576. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-015-1245-x>